

D6.3 - INITIAL EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Sound Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is critical in order to enable the successful exploitation and deployment of all SUSTRACK assets. Therefore, the consortium of SUSTRACK places great emphasis on managing IPR in the framework of the project, with a view to effectively pave the way for the smooth exploitation and sustainability of its results following its completion.

Along these lines, the current report presents **the initial version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (ESP) of the SUSTRACK Project**. It sheds light on the key terms pertaining to the management and protection of intellectual property and lays down the main components of the relevant methodology to be applied throughout the project.

A preliminary description of the project results, along with initial identification of the contributing partners, protection types and access rights are provided within the report. An overview of SUSTRACK's assets as envisioned at this stage of the project is also presented, as well as the initial considerations of Background and Foreground IP Knowledge, as currently perceived by the project partners. The methodology applied is supported by the IPR Matrix that facilitates registration of all background and foreground IPR and helps the timely identification and resolution of any potential conflict in this respect.

The report will be further elaborated and updated on a regular basis as the project progresses. The final version will be delivered by the end of the project (M36), to guide post-project exploitation of SUSTRACK's results. As such, several elements presented in this document are considered exploratory, preliminary and subject to revision and change; therefore, their status will be validated during the final versions of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D6.4, M36).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION	11
1.1	Purpose and Scope	11
1.2	Document structure	11
2.	IPR MANAGEMENT OVERVIEW	12
2.1	Objectives	12
2.2	Definitions	13
2.2.1	Background IP	13
2.2.2	Foreground IP	13
2.2.3	Exploitable Results	14
2.2.4	Access Rights	14
2.2.5	Protection of Results	15
3.	APPROACH	18
3.1	Preparation Stage	19
3.1.1	Grant Agreement	19
3.1.2	Consortium Agreement	19
3.2	Implementation Stage	20
3.2.1	Background Identification	20
3.2.2	Foreground Identification	21
3.2.3	Results' ownership	21
3.2.4	Protection of results	21
3.2.5	Exploitation of results	22
3.2.6	Dissemination of results	22
3.3	Post project Stage	22
3.4	Role of the Exploitation Manager	23
3.5	Knowledge Management of the project	23

3.6	IP Conflicts	24
4.	IPR MATRIX METHODOLOGY	24
4.1	Identification of Background IP	26
4.2	Identification of Foreground IP.....	26
4.3	Identification of exploitable results	27
5.	OVERVIEW OF SUSTRACK’S ASSETS, BACKGROUND AND FOREGROUND IP	28
5.1	Identified Assets of SUSTRACK.....	28
5.2	Background	29
5.3	Foreground IP	29
6.	EXPLOITATION PLANS PER ASSET	44
6.1	WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios	44
6.2	Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines	45
6.3	Case study analyses	46
6.4	WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities	47
6.5	WP6 Co-creation activities.....	48
6.6	Reports and deliverables	49
6.7	Event format package	50
6.8	Scenario simulations generated using the Green Economy Model.....	51
7.	EXPLOITATION PLANS PER PARTNER	51
8.	INNOVATION MANAGEMENT STRATEGY	53
9.	CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD	55

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. IPR Management stages.....19

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Access Rights.....15

Table 2: Indicative list of protection instruments21

Table 3 Structure of the IPR Matrix25

Table 4: IPR Matrix Background Template.....26

Table 5: IPR Matrix Foreground Template26

Table 6: IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template.....27

Table 7: Identified Assets28

Table 8: SUSTRACK’s Identified IP BG30

Table 9: SUSTRACK’s Identified IP FG34

Table 10: Exploitation plan for WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios44

Table 11. Actions needed for the exploitation of the Policy Portfolio Scenarios45

Table 12. Exploitation plan for Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines45

Table 13. Actions needed for the exploitation of Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines46

Table 14. Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses.....46

Table 15. Actions needed for Case Study analyses47

Table 16. Exploitation plan for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities47

Table 17. Actions needed for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities48

Table 18. Exploitation plan for WP6 Co-creation activities.....48

Table 19. Actions needed for WP6 Co-creation activities.....49

Table 20. Exploitation plan for reports and deliverables49

Table 21. Actions needed for reports and deliverables.....50

Table 22. Exploitation plan for Event format package50

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

Table 23. Actions needed for event format package50

Table 24. Exploitation plan for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model51

Table 25. Actions needed for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model.....51

Table 26. Individual exploitation plans52

List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EPC	European Patent Convention
ER	Exploitable Results
EU	European Union
FG	Foreground
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
MML	Mobilization and Mutual Learning
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PR	Project Result
R&D	Research and Development
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The SUSTRACK partners focus on producing results that will be sustainable after the project's completion and ensuring that innovative ideas, methodologies, and results of the project will be fully identified, preserved and considered in terms of the wider availability to all relevant stakeholders. Thus, the consortium defines basic principles, from the early stages of the project, that will yield a solid management framework for the Background (BG), as well as the Foreground (FG) Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of SUSTRACK. The SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability Plan sets the ground for monitoring the protection of IP and IPR within the consortium, which eventually will support the creation of value as regards the exploitable results of the project and facilitate successful innovation and deployment. The current report presents the **initial version of the SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability Plan** which aims to identify the project's key assets, set the premises for the determination of their underlying IPR, as well as for the development of a common understanding regarding their exploitation framework after the end of the project.

1.2 Document structure

The initial version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan has the following structure:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated as well as its targets and structure.
- **Chapter 2** clarifies the key terms pertaining to the IPR management of the project, defines the underlying objectives and explains the main intellectual property protection instruments to be employed.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of SUSTRACK and describes the methodology to be followed in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed in order to identify the SUSTRACK background and foreground IP, as perceived at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 5** offers a preliminary overview of the project's assets to be co-created, as identified at this stage of the project, as well as the background and foreground IPs as perceived by all SUSTRACK partners.
- **Chapter 6** presents exploitation plans per assets
- **Chapter 7** introduces individual exploitation plans
- **Chapter 8** describes briefly how innovation management is articulated in SUSTRACK and how the relevant stakeholders interact with the innovation management process.
- **Chapter 9** concludes on the next steps towards the exploitation of the assets of the project.

The SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability Plan will be updated and further elaborated on a systematic basis throughout the project. Specifically, a final version of D6.4 is expected at the end of the project (M36). This will include the description of the project's final assets, as well as the consortium's plans regarding their IPR protection and their main exploitation routes that will facilitate their exploitation after the end of the project.

2. IPR MANAGEMENT OVERVIEW

2.1 Objectives

SUSTRACK's Exploitation and Sustainability Plan objectives reflect the need to protect all project assets with a view of managing efficiently all the outcomes that will stem from the project's activities and ensuring the wider availability to all relevant stakeholders and, where relevant, the deployment of SUSTRACK's exploitable results after the project's completion. To this end, the main objectives of the SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability Plan are the following:

- **Define** and **agree** on the SUSTRACK IPR management methodology to be followed within the context of the project.
- **Identify** the assets that will emerge from the activities foreseen within the lifecycle of SUSTRACK thus, determining an assets' portfolio from the early stages of the project.
- **Develop** a common understanding among SUSTRACK partners, concerning terms and issues of the Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) IP and respective access rights.
- **Conceptualize** a preliminary frame of the IP protection that will be employed in each identified exploitable result of SUSTRACK.
- **Prevent** and, if not possible to prevent in all cases, define and eventually dissolve any possible conflicts in IP within the consortium and beyond.
- **Establish** common guiding routes and actions within the consortium so as to safeguard the smooth operation of the IPR strategies to be implemented.

The Exploitation and Sustainability Plan is setting out how the following elements related to IP in SUSTRACK are to be managed within the project's context, with a view to creating a path for post-project exploitation of the relevant assets:

- Background IP
- Foreground IP
- Exploitable Results
- Access Rights
- Protection of Results
- Dissemination

The above-mentioned key concepts are normally considered for designing the Exploitation, Sustainability Plan of Horizon Europe projects. Definitions of these concepts are provided in the definition section below and have been communicated to and agreed upon by all SUSTRACK partners.

2.2 Definitions

2.2.1 Background IP

Background IP can be defined as data, know-how or information - including any rights - owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the commencement of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project's assets.¹ The background needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the underlying results must be accessible to the other project partners on a royalty-free basis. Under this frame, all project partners must identify the background as pertinent to the project actions and grant access rights to this IP.² The background of a project can be identified and agreed:

- (i) Within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, or
- (ii) in a separate agreement ("agreement on the background").

In this respect, there are two main aspects to consider when dealing with the background of a project:³

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the assets that each project partner provides to the consortium and which are imperative for the successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and alignment with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

2.2.2 Foreground IP

Foreground refers to the results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge.⁴ These results comprise any tangible or intangible output of the project's actions which can be protectable or not. In this respect, foreground IP can arise and be obtained from project partners in order to protect and exploit the underlying exploitable results of the project. It includes intellectual

¹ See Article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement

² See Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the SUSTRACK background and the access rights granted.

³ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al., *European IP Helpdesk : successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe : boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>.

⁴ For a detailed definition of the Foreground see: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/glossary/foreground>. Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as foreground.

SUSTRACK's Grant Agreement establishes that the results of the project are owned by the project partner who generates them.⁵ Given the collaborative nature of the project, some results can be jointly developed by several partners. In this case, **joint ownership can arise among the contributing partners and is subject to the agreement on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership.** Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement,⁶ it would be best practice for partners to establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership. Each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the joint-owned results unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement.

2.2.3 Exploitable Results

The exploitation of project results means the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned (e.g. in other research activities; or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process; or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities).⁷ Under this scheme, an **exploitable result** is defined as a project result (expected or achieved) that meets the following two conditions:

- Has commercial/social/academic relevance;
- Can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (e.g. product, process, service, etc.).⁸

Therefore, exploitable results can be a combination or part of a foreground result(s). Not all foreground items may meet the above conditions.⁹ Furthermore, exploitable results are not necessarily market ready; they may require further R&D, engineering and validation before becoming commercially exploitable.

2.2.4 Access Rights

Access rights refer to one partner's rights for requesting access to another project partner's background and foreground to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results.

⁵ See article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement, Annex 5

⁶ See article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement, Annex 5

⁷ European Commission, Glossary, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

⁸ A patent for licensing is also an exploitable result.

⁹ European Commission, Communication, Dissemination And Exploitation Why They All Matter And What Is The Difference?, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

Additionally, access rights can be used as long as they are needed for exploiting the project's results. The provisions governing access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follow specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Access rights within SUSTRACK are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Access Rights

Purpose of access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free Unless otherwise agreed by participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free
Exploitation of Own results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subject to individual agreement Granted under fair and reasonable conditions 	

2.2.5 Protection of Results

It should be noted that when considering IP protection, IP assets can be protected by several types of IPR, and therefore, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner.

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the frame of SUSTRACK, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks;
- Patents;
- Utility models;
- Copyrights;
- Trade secrets;
- Confidentiality agreements.

Further details about each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

Trademarks and service marks

Trade Marks

A trade mark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered.¹⁰ Trade marks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the

¹⁰ For the definition of trademark in Europe, see: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last Accessed: 13/4/2023.

products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trade mark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it should inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that consumers can trust in a given enterprise, not necessarily known to them, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are confronted not only with a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend more and more to be offered on a national and international scale. There is therefore a need for signs that enable consumers to distinguish between different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc. These signs are called service marks and fulfil essentially the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs which are very similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria could be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a very short amendment to the existing trademark law or simply by providing for the protection of service marks under the provisions of the trademark law.¹¹

Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) that offer a new technical solution or facilitate a new way of doing something. The patent holder has the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application.¹²

The patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Additionally, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or permit them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally (e.g. European), and may also be used in non-patented territories (although in such cases they would not enjoy the patent protection). Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that owners do not hold exclusive rights any longer. Therefore, it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others.¹³

Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law, and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68f.

¹² Definition of patents in the European context retrieved from: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17.

their authorisation, for a limited period.¹⁴ The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals.¹⁵

Copyrights

Copyright (or author's right) is the term used to describe the economic and moral rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works. It is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original.¹⁶ There is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, there are several works usually covered by copyright at an international level:¹⁷

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper articles;
- Computer programmes, databases;
- Films, musical compositions, and choreographies;
- Artistic works such as paintings, drawings, etc; and
- Advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator's reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made "pirated" goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition.

Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information that provides a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that could be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It could include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable

¹⁴ Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

¹⁵ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁶ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁷ Definition of copyrights in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last accessed:13/4/2023.

as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes.¹⁸

Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely important issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up stage to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is generally a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitate the project development and ensure the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and security to an organization that is about to share or make available information to another organization by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement could be a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge.¹⁹

There are specific criteria to determine a confidentiality agreement as legally enforceable:

- The information must be secret, i.e. not readily accessible to people that normally deal with this kind of information;
- It must have commercial value;
- The owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect it.

3. APPROACH

Throughout the SUSTRACK project, key IP and exploitation and sustainability management will build on the pillars of identifying a common understanding concerning the background, foreground, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability plan applies a comprehensive framework which separates the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

1. Grant Agreement preparation stage;
2. Project implementation stage;
3. Post-project stage.

In this respect, Figure 1 illustrates the IPR management stages, as considered within SUSTRACK.

¹⁸ Definition of trade secrets in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

¹⁹ See confidentiality agreements on the WIPO website: https://www.wipo.int/sme/en/documents/disclosing_inf_fulltext.html. Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

Figure 1. IPR Management stages

3.1 Preparation Stage

Both the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement constitute documents which include a description of several issues related to IPR. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues within the project partners. Thus, **any further advancements regarding IPR actions to be put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions.**

3.1.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project. It is signed between the EC and the SUSTRACK partners and represents the main contractual basis for SUSTRACK while its main points and sections which refer to IPR are included in article 16 “Intellectual property rights (IPR) – background and results –access rights and rights of use”. Under this scheme, the management of the SUSTRACK IP is regulated, whereas access rights and obligations related to the background are set. In addition, the Grant Agreement defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project’s generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination outcomes. Lastly, the SUSTRACK GA defines transferability and access rights to results.

3.1.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement constitutes a contract among the partners of the SUSTRACK consortium which aims to define rights and obligations during the partnership for the purposes of carrying out the project’s foreseen actions and activities.²⁰ The Consortium Agreement minimises the

²⁰ See IPR helpdesk for the definition of Consortium Agreement.

probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities during the project and defines the access rights to be granted to the partners concerning the project. In addition, it outlines rights and responsibilities among the consortium members concerning issues of the IP.

The SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement's main points and sections referring to IPR are included in:

- **Section 8 “Results”**, that sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination.
- **Section 9 “Access Rights”**, which clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for exploitation and dissemination purposes.
- **Attachment 1 “Background included”** that presents the initial list of usable backgrounds.

3.2 Implementation Stage

During the implementation stage of SUSTRACK, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the SUSTRACK partners to organise the results/assets management of the project. As the project continues, the focus will be on foreground identification, assets' ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as on the exploitation and commercialisation of the project's results. The SUSTRACK IPR management emphasises establishing robust handling procedures of the IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project in order to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

Therefore, partners should focus on two different points:

- **Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.**
- **Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate and exploit the project's assets.**

In this respect, key IP-related issues in the SUSTRACK implementation phase include:

- **Background Identification**
- **Foreground Identification**
- **Results' ownership**
- **Protection of results**
- **Exploitation of results**
- **Dissemination of results**

3.2.1 Background Identification

During the first stages of SUSTRACK is vital to identify the relevant knowledge, know-how and partners' data, that constitute the background of the project. Under this framework, the underlying background could be attached to the generated assets of the project, which, eventually, will help the determination of access rights, ownership issues and IPR.

3.2.2 Foreground Identification

A core process of the SUSTRACK IP management is the project assets' identification to create a concrete mapping of the projects' assets and enhance the SUSTRACK IP portfolio. Therefore, all IP valuable assets within the project must be identified, listed, named, described and analysed in a systematic way.

3.2.3 Results' ownership

Partners have been asked (through the SUSTRACK IPR Matrix) to elaborate further on the provisions of the Consortium Agreement regarding the results' ownership. Special attention will be paid to **handling joint ownership issues**.

3.2.4 Protection of results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and assets developed under the frame of SUSTRACK depends on the protection of the project's results. In particular, the project's results must adequately be protected if:²¹

- The project's results can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and;
- Protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

On this note, **when considering IP protection, SUSTRACK partners must consider their own interests along with the interests of the consortium**. Project partners should safeguard the identified exploitable SUSTRACK results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer a protection period within a suitable geographical territory. The geographical territory should be agreed upon by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory in which the identified exploitable SUSTRACK results will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement regarding this matter.

Table 2 illustrates an indicative list of different protection instruments. The ones most applicable to the SUSTRACK project are highlighted, as considering the CSA nature of the project, it is not expected to employ all the instruments in the list. Furthermore, additional protection instruments can be used when deemed suitable as the project activities progress.

Table 2: Indicative list of protection instruments

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software ²²	X	X	X		X

²¹ See: <https://cms.eurice.eu/storage/uploads/news/files/ip-management-in-collab-horizon-projects.pdf>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

²² Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk.

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale or commercialization of IP in the form of products and services. IP utilization is vital for prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it could contribute to supporting the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that the IP protection of an asset is not always mandatory.

3.2.5 Exploitation of results

The identified exploitable results and assets of SUSTRACK will be effectively exploited for commercial or any other relevant use as foreseen during the SUSTRACK project. In particular, the SUSTRACK consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in:

- i) Further research activities;
- ii) Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- iii) Creating and providing a service;
- iv) Using them in standardisation activities.

3.2.6 Dissemination of results

SUSTRACK partners are set to select the appropriate means for the dissemination of the project's results (e.g. scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, open access, etc.), based on the conditions set forth in the CA²³ and in other specific confidentiality agreements. All partners should be aware that they should first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of the underlying result.

3.3 Post project Stage

At the project's formal conclusion in M36, D6.4 Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan will be submitted. It will include the final outline of the use which the SUSTRACK consortium intends to make its exploitable foreground (including its final description and sector of application) and the related plans and time frame for their exploitation.

D6.4 will describe further the activities that will be developed to deploy the dissemination and exploitation of the project's achievements and the activities that aim to ensure the sustainability of the project's results. Additionally, D6.4 will include the final findings regarding IP issues and

²³ See Section 8.4 of the SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement.

the final update of the IPR Matrix presenting in detail the applied and registered intellectual property rights.

The aforementioned deliverable will present the final advanced strategy for the exploitation and management of IPR and the sustainability after the project ends, including also the concrete chosen commercialisation streams as well as the business plan.

3.4 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The Exploitation Manager (EM) is responsible for defining SUSTRACK's Exploitation and Sustainability Plan. The tasks include preparing the respective reports and ensuring that innovative ideas which come up during the project will be thoroughly examined and assessed for potential exploitation, while at the same time, all project's BG and FG IPs are properly managed. To this end, the Exploitation Manager (PEDAL) will be in close communication with the Project Coordinator (UNIT) and the Project Management Committee (PMC) to ensure the optimal management of all IP assets.

The Exploitation Manager and the Project Coordinator will be responsible for the organization and management issues of SUSTRACK's IPR strategy implementation. With that said, it is considered as being a good practice for a partner to inform and consult the EM and the PC accordingly before deciding whether to protect the results stemming from its underlying activities or not - particularly if the partner is considering a potential joint IP scheme.

Lastly, the Exploitation Manager has also a mediation role in case of IP conflicts (see Section 3.6), monitors project activities and feeds the development of the subsequent versions of this report in the context of SUSTRACK.

3.5 Knowledge Management of the project

The management of the IP constitutes an integral part of the overall SUSTRACK project management structure and thus it is important to establish permanent IP monitoring during the project. In this respect, an efficient IPR management methodology should define, from the early stages of the project, the procedures under which newly generated/identified results will be handled during the SUSTRACK's lifecycle.

Efficient management of IP in SUSTRACK will be achieved by adopting a process able to identify IP results as well as to determine their adequate handling and protection. In this respect, it is essential to establish mechanisms that will guarantee that IP information is reliable and timely captured. In case WP Leaders identify a new asset that will be generated under their respective WP activities, the Exploitation Manager should be informed accordingly.

The SUSTRACK Exploitation Manager and the PC, together with the partners producing the newly identified asset, constitute the parties that will handle the screening and managing of any newly identified assets and their corresponding IP issues. The Exploitation Manager will direct the consortium partners to establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategy based on the nature of the newly identified asset and the purposes of the SUSTRACK consortium.

To facilitate this process, the SUSTRACK Exploitation and Sustainability plan foresees to create and update a living IPR Matrix to be revised and extended with new pieces of assets and project results (FG).

3.6 IP Conflicts

In order to proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners will be well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process not only via the IPR Matrix but also through the help of the Exploitation Manager. In this respect, project partners will identify their IPR assets, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to SUSTRACK's exploitable results according to the principle rights and obligations defined in the CA of the project.²⁴

The Exploitation Manager will provide assistance for the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g. on new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and exploitation claims?

In case of IP conflict, the Exploitation Manager will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and pro-actively find solutions and sign written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, an internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of the SUSTRACK's CA. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, a further mediation process in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules will be applied.²⁵

4. IPR MATRIX METHODOLOGY

The IPR Matrix will be used in the framework of the project to define the main IPR issues related to the Exploitation and sustainability strategy. This approach will facilitate the consortium partners to identify the background, foreground, and exploitable results. In addition, the IP

²⁴ See Section 8 of the SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement.

²⁵ See Section 11.8 of the SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement.

protection measures, and the necessary agreements will be defined to ensure the successful exploitation of the project outcomes even after the completion of the project.

The IPR methodology follows four (4) interconnected steps:

1. **Identification of the Background IP** and definition of the access rights of the consortium partners
2. Preliminary **identification of the foreground IP** that will be produced in the framework of the project's activities.
3. Initial **identification of the exploitable assets/results** that will be produced in the framework of the project and the interest for their commercialisation.
4. **Definition of the IPR protection** of the identified exploitable assets/results that can be potentially commercially exploited by the consortium partners.

At this early stage of the project, the objective of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan of SUSTRACK is to define the main assets on the one hand and identify, to the extent possible, the FG and BG IPs of the project along with their corresponding access rights on the other hand. During the later stages of the project's implementation, the IPR methodology will be devised accordingly, in order to capture and integrate the evolvement of the identified results and the IPR approach of the project. In particular, the identification of exploitable assets would yield the need to establish an ownership regime among project partners for each one of the exploitable results. In addition, rules and conditions to get access to exploitable results need also to be considered. Finally, validation of the IPR needs to be meticulously employed. Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 Structure of the IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner's Background • Contributing Partner • Short Description of BG • Type of Protection • How will it be utilised within SUSTRACK? • Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK • Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK • Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FG# • Project Outcome / Achievement/ Result • Related WP • Contributing Partners • Short Description of FG • Related BG# (BG owner) • Type of Protection • Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK • Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results • Conditions to Use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ER# • Exploitable result • Main partner • Further contributing partner(s) • Related FG# • Related project task/deliverable (if applicable) • Related BG# (BG owner) • Proposition for the ER-owner • Short description of the ER • Relevance for IP Protection

4.1 Identification of Background IP

During the first stage of the IPR Matrix, the Background that will be used during the implementation of the project was identified (Table 4).

Table 4: IPR Matrix Background Template

#	Relevant Background (the name of the Background)	Contributing Partner	BG identifier	Short description of BG	Type of protection (e.g., patent, copyright, TM, Utility model)	Conditions to use within SUSTRACK (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA..)	Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK E.g. Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes on what conditions?	Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK's results (Yes/ No)
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Multiple information regarding the Background IP is recorded in the respective template. In the second column of the table, a short name of the Background is given. Then, the responsible partner is mentioned, and a number is assigned related to the Work package and the number of assets. In the 5th column of the table, a short more detailed description of the BG is offered. Furthermore, the partners define the Type of protection in terms of patents, utility models, copyrights, trade and service marks, trade secrets, creative commons licenses, and confidentiality agreements, among others. In column seven (7), the partners define how this BG will be used in the framework of the project, and then in columns eight (8) and nine (9) describe the conditions under which the consortium partners and the stakeholders outside the consortium respectively can use the BG. Finally, the partners should state their interest in further exploitation of the BG in the framework of the project through the produced results.

The background IP was registered by the project partners by M6, as perceived at that stage of the project. The results are presented in the next chapter.

4.2 Identification of Foreground IP

In the second stage of the IPR Matrix, the partners have identified the Foreground that will be produced during the project's activities (Table 5).

Table 5: IPR Matrix Foreground Template

WP	#	Project result (PRI)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	FG number	Type of protection (e.g., patent, copyright, TM, Utility model, CC licence)	Conditions to use within SUSTRACK (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA..)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/ No)	Conditions to use after the end of project (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA..)
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The above template is used by the consortium partners to identify the foreground IP. In the first four columns, the SUSTRACK project achievements are listed along with the respective WP. Then, the main contributing partner is mentioned. Usually, if an FG comes as a direct result of a Task, then the main partner is the Task leader. In addition, the rest of the contributing partners are also mentioned. Similarly, the contributing partners are usually the partners contributing to the Task that the FG emerges from. In the 7th column, the number of the related Background IP is mentioned while in column eight (8) is given a short description of the FG. Furthermore, a Foreground number is assigned to the respective FG. Similarly, to the background identification template, the partners also define the type of protection, the conditions under which the FG can be used by the consortium partners and the interest for the commercialization through the project results. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the end of the project shall be indicated by the project partners.

The identified Foreground IP up until M6 can be found in the respective chapter.

4.3 Identification of exploitable results

In the third stage and based on the identified FG the consortium partners will define the exploitable results and the IPR management procedures:

- i) Protection
- ii) Definition of access rights
- iii) Exploitation pathways

The main aim of this third stage of the IPR Matrix where the exploitable results and the main contributors will be defined will be:

- To identify IP ownership and exploitation claims, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection, in order to timely make the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g. for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

Table 6 will be used throughout the whole duration of the project in order to deploy the third stage of the IPR Matrix and identify the exploitable results.

Table 6: IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template

ER#	Exploitable Result	Short description of ER	Main partner	Contributing Partner(s)	Related FG	Related BG	ER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	(which exploitation path is most promising)
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In the first three columns, the number, a short name and a brief description of the exploitable results will be mentioned. In the next two columns, the main responsible partner and the rest contributing partners will be listed. In columns 6th and 7th, the number of the related FG and BG will be indicated. In addition, in the next column, the proposed owner of the exploitable result will be defined, while in column nine (9) the relevance for IP protection will be indicated by the responsible partner. The next five (5) columns indicate the five (5) different categories of exploitation claims.

- **M:** Making a product and selling it.
- **U:** Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - To develop something else for sale; or
 - For R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.
- **L:** Licensing the project result to third parties.
- **S:** Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.
- **O:** Others

The partner responsible for the exploitable results with the support of the contributing partners, the coordinator and the exploitation manager shall choose which exploitation claims best fit the ER. In the final column, the most promising exploitation claim shall be indicated.

5. OVERVIEW OF SUSTRACK'S ASSETS, BACKGROUND AND FOREGROUND IP

5.1 Identified Assets of SUSTRACK

Table 7 presents the identified assets and their short description as defined by the consortium partners during these early stages of the project.

Table 7: Identified Assets

No.	Asset	Description
1	WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios	4 of these scenarios will be carried out and will involve the collection and review of the current and prospective policy instruments that might influence the sustainable transition at the EU, country (and possibly regional) levels.
2	Policy recommendations and guidelines	These will be produced for each case study summarising the findings for each of the carbon intensive sectors and providing indications of pressing actions and sustainability considerations to support the sustainable transition at the national and EU levels. These will be the main output of T5.3
3	Case studies analyses	Four (4) sectors were identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system and they include; the construction sector, the textile sector, the (fine) chemical sector, and (d) the plastic sector. The objective for this will be to test whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings will also contribute to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allow for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes will be validated during the IMPLEMENT conference.
4	WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities (including; capacity building for local stakeholders; tools and methodologies)	W These capacity building activities will take place to boost the know - how of local stakeholders in each respective partner country and to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural). The results of the policy scenario development and modelling (WP4, T4.3) and the identification of local policy priorities will enable stakeholders to identify actionable steps along the most suitable transition pathway while identifying the pitfalls and opportunities of this pathway in the respective sector (i.e., construction, chemical, textile or plastic sector) and country.
5	WP6 Co-creation activities (including; 3 international conferences (EU level), 6 national conferences and 3 mutual learning workshops)	3 EU Level conferences will be organized to offer support to partners in specific task-related activities with stakeholders (e.g., co-creation) primarily aimed at sharing both the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK and co-creating stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions.6 national conferences will be organized to fine-tune the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and co-create policy recommendations (both sector- and countryspecific). The local DEPLOY conferences will also empower stakeholders through capacity-building activities (T4.3 and T5.2) 2 MML

No.	Asset	Description
		workshops will also be organized. The first MML (M3) workshop will be to engage with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to share methodologies, lessons and findings. And the second MML workshop will be to provide insight to refine the SUSTRACK results and recommendations, thereby facilitating the greatest exploitation of the project outcomes (M30).
6	Reports and deliverables	All project activities will be accounted for through the publication of the project results through the project reports and deliverables
7	Event format package	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced gamified applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MML.
8	Toolkits	Combination of all knowledge assets with explanations produced by the project and useful for their replication and exploitation
9	Monitoring and assessment framework	This will consist in guidance for decision-makers that explains the approach of monitoring and assessing the transition towards bio-based circular economy
10	Monitoring and assessment dashboard	This will consist in a ready-to-use tool to map outcomes of the assessment of bio-based circular systems as described in the monitoring framework

5.2 Background

The project partners preliminary identified the background IP to be used to achieve the objectives of SUSTRACK. The Background IP is presented in Table 8.

5.3 Foreground IP

Preliminary identification of the Foreground IP took place during the initial stages of the project and can be found in Table 9. Additional updates or modifications are expected in the updated version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, which will correspond to the progress of the project and the produced results and know-how.

Table 8: SUSTRACK's Identified IP BG

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK	Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK results
1	“European Bioeconomy Network” database and mailing lists	FVA	BG1	“European Bioeconomy Network” database and mailing lists	Copyright	Will be used for project activities by FVA, but will not be shared among partners	Will be used for project’s activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
2	“European Bioeconomy Network” website, knowledge and partnership	FVA	BG2	“European Bioeconomy Network” website, knowledge and partnership	None	Will be used for project activities by FVA	Will be used for project’s activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
3	Biovoices social media	FVA	BG3	Biovoices social media channels	None	Will not be directly used by the project, but can be deployed for joint activities and initiatives	Will be used by FVA, but will not be subject to	N/A

						with BIOGov.net social media channels	exploitation by the consortium	
4	BioArt Gallery	FVA	BG4	The BIOArt Gallery is a collection of stunning pictures of the most promising feedstock and its related bioeconomy applications in everyday life. It offers an innovative approach to showcasing to the public some examples of bio-based products and applications currently available in the market through several examples: cosmetics, nutraceuticals, tissues, toys and sports, disposable tableware, cleaning products, gadgets, and much more.	Copyright	Will be used for project activities by FVA	Will be used for project's activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
5	Bioeconomy Village	FVA	BG5	The Bioeconomy Village is a collection of more than 350 bio-based products and aims at raising public awareness, improving knowledge on bio-based products and promoting the applications and benefits of the circular bioeconomy and sustainability, encouraging dialogue, discussion and sharing	None	Will be used for project activities by FVA	Will be used for project's activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A

				between the general public and representatives of universities, research centres, projects, companies, associations and start-ups.				
6	FVA Database of contacts in the bioeconomy sector	FVA	BG6	FVA Database of contacts in the bioeconomy sector	None	Will be used by FVA for the project's activities, but not shared with the partners	Will be used for project's activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
7	Methodology to quantify soil impacts	CIRCE	BG7	Methodology to quantify the global agricultural crop footprint including soil impacts	None	It will be owned and used exclusively by CIRCE for Task 2.2.	Developed by CIRCE before starting of SUSTRACK project. It will be owned and used exclusively by CIRCE for exploiting the results.	Yes
8	Methodology and model for analysing the cross-sectoral	KE	BG8	The Green Economy Model (GEM) is a System Dynamics based model that was developed to analyse the cross-sectoral impacts of green	None	Will be used for project activities by KE	Will be used for the project's activities by KE, but will not be	N/A

	impacts of policy			development strategies. It allows for simulating the cross-sectoral impacts of policy interventions and thereby enables a more systemic assessment of the sustainability of specific policies/policy packages as well as related costs, avoided costs and added benefits.			subject to further exploitation by the consortium	
9	Methodology to develop portfolio policy scenarios based on a template	DBFZ	BG9	Methodology to develop policy portfolio scenarios. It will contain a template, including policies relevant to the transition from a linear and fossil-based economy towards a circular and bio-based one. The template will be filled out via partners and will be applied in the GEM.	None	Will be used for project activities by DBFZ	Free to use	No
10	Policies for technology transfer	DBFZ	BG10	There is an institutional internal policy for technology transfer	None	Is the baseline for the institutional internal work but followed within the project's activities but not usable/shareable within the SUSTRACK Project	Not usable outside DBFZ or SUSTRACK	No

Table 9: SUSTRACK's Identified IP FG

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
1	1.1	Report on the literature gaps and trade-offs	-	UNIT	KE, UNIFE, BAM, TECNALIA, UGENT	-	This public report will provide an overview of the work conducted within Task 1.1. Specifically, it will present findings obtained by reviewing and analysing existing literature and recent EU surveys on trends with respect to the environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive, and fossil-based economy.	FG1.1	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
1	1.3	Report on the prioritisation of the identified limits, as well as the preliminary	-	UNIT	CIRCE, BAM, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, DBFZ, KE,WR,	-	This public report will provide an overview of the work conducted within Task 1.3. Specifically, it will present previously identified limits that	FG1.3	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
		guidelines and policy recommendations					will be prioritized through pairwise comparisons based on expert judgements.					
2	2.1	System of monitor and assessment of the benefits of the sustainable transition	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 - monitoring and assessment dashboard	TECN ALIA	FVA, DBFZ, BAM, UNIT, WR, KE, PC, CIRCE	BG7 (CIRCE)	Framework and dashboard for decision makers to monitor and assess circularity and the sustainability impacts of the transition at different levels	FG2.1	Creative Commons Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use
2	2.2	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 - monitoring and assessment dashboard	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TEC, UNIT	-	(a) the development of methods to evaluate soil quality and other land-use impacts; (b) the linking of micro- and macro-modelling approaches (e.g., life cycle assessment of circularity, environmental and socio-economic impacts for key	FG2.2	Creative Commons Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
							sectors, economy-wide assessment of material flows, national/regional assessment of the environment, society, and economy); and (c) the quantification of monetisation factors to estimate externalities related to environmental and social impacts and the monetary value of ecosystem service flows.					
2	2.3	Advancement of sustainability assessment knowledge: final	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 - monitoring and assessment dashboard	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TEC, UNIT	-	This public report will be an update of Deliverable 2.2 taking account of all insights derived during the project, particularly in	FG2.3	Creative Commons License	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
							the testing of new indicators and metrics in the case studies performed in WP3.					
2	2.4	Analysis and development of sustainability thresholds	Sustainability thresholds defined for some indicators	BAM	TEC, UNIT, WR, DBFZ, FVA, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT	-	This public report will identify and propose, when possible, thresholds for the indicators to be included in the framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition. The identification of thresholds will be done by conducting desk research complemented by different interactions with stakeholders.	FG2.5	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
3	3.4	Overall findings,	#3 To assess the	WR	UGENT, UNIT, CIRCE, PC, KE,		The results of the case studies will be		None	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
		recommendations and conclusions from case studies	environmental, social and economic impacts of the sustainable transition, with regard to selected case studies.		TEC, DBFZ, BAM	-	generalised to provide conclusions and recommendations for the four bio-based sectors.	FG3.4				
4	4.1	Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages	- Template for collecting policy instruments - Collection of policy instruments - Generated scenarios for each case study	DBFZ	UNIT, BAM, WR, TEC, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT	BG9/BG10	The methodological background of the scenario development is differentiated within different steps and deliverables. 1. Development of a template to collect policy instruments related to the case studies 2. Evaluation of the collected policy tools and analysis of the status quo of	FG4.1	Creative Commons Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
							policy tools already in force (baseline scenario) 3. Development of sustainable BE scenarios in cooperation with other work packages for each case study 4. Report about the methodology used and information collected about policy tools.					
4	4.3	Report presenting the results of all simulations and documentation of the model	a. Description of scenarios b. Comparison of scenarios c. Analysis of cross-sectoral policy impacts in the transitioning	KE	-	-	The report will present the simulations that were used to assess the systemic impacts of policies aiming to facilitate the transition toward a sustainable bioeconomy.	FG4.3	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			scenarios d. Insight into the impact of policy, including investment requirements, avoided costs and added benefits resulting from the transition				Documentation of the model will be provided to ensure that the reader understands the methodological foundations used to generate the results.					
5	5.1	Final policy brief: policy priorities to support the sustainable transition and examples of good policies	#5. To identify policy priorities, define corresponding policy actions and provide recommendations to policy makers	WR	UNIT, DBFZ, CIRCE, PEDAL, FVA, KE, BAM, TEC	-	This public report will present the policy priorities to support the sustainable transition to a circular bioeconomy with a focus on EU policy instruments and instruments available at the national and regional levels. It will	FG5.2	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
							make recommendations for good policy examples. The derived policy priorities and examples of good policies will be based on a systematic review of policy instruments and a validation process with stakeholders in co-creation workshops that will take place at the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences of SUSTRACK.					
6	6.1	Identity	website, brand, logo, social media, promotional	FVA	All partners	-	The SUSTRACK brand enhanced throughout the duration of the project	FG5.6	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			video and video teasers, factsheets, infographic cards, dashboard visual identity				facilitating the dissemination and exploitation of the project's outcome					
6	6.2-6.3	Event format package	Innovative co-creation workshops, policy roundtables, capacity building	FVA	All partners	BG1, BG6	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced gamified applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MML.	FG5.7	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use
6	6.1	Toolkits	Deployment package of SUSTRACK toolkits	FVA	All partners	-	Combination of all knowledge assets with explanations produced by the	FG5.8	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use

D6.3 Initial exploitation and sustainability plan

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
							project and useful for their replication and exploitation					

6. EXPLOITATION PLANS PER ASSET

In this section of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, the main assets of the SUSTRACK project are described, along with the main contributors to their development. Information is also provided on who their intended users are, the benefits they stand to gain from exploiting that asset as well as on potential exploitation routes. In parallel, the main creator of each asset indicates any foreseeable action that may be needed to facilitate the intended exploitation route(s) of the asset, concisely outlining what needs to be done, when and by whom.

The above information is presented in two tables for each asset:

- One table summarising the exploitation plan of that asset.
- A second table summarising any actions needed for the exploitation of that asset.

Each asset is presented in a dedicated sub-section below.

6.1 WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios

The exploitation plan for WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Exploitation plan for WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios

Asset description	4 of these scenarios will be carried out and will involve the collection and review of the current and prospective policy instruments that might influence the sustainable transition at the EU, country (and possibly regional) levels.
Creators of Asset	DBFZ, UNIT, BAM, WR, TEC, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Policy makers: A overview of the current policy instruments impacting the case studies will support to adapt and develop these further + overview of opportunities for policy instruments to integrate and support a sustainable transition to a circular bioeconomy. Industrial players: Overview of actual and prospective policy instruments can have impacts on their business cases. Civil society: Overview of policy instruments influencing the sector + what policy instruments could support the development of the sector. General interest from civil society exists. Modellers: the scenario settings (assumptions) van be implemented in further models and in this way the assumptions of the policy landscape of a sustainable transition.
Intended exploitation route	Dissemination

The actions needed for the exploitation of the Policy Portfolio Scenarios are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Actions needed for the exploitation of the Policy Portfolio Scenarios

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of Policy portfolio scenarios	DBFZ and partners involved in the scenario development and workshop.	M12 + M14/15 End report of the task

6.2 Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

The exploitation plan for Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines is presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Exploitation plan for Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

Asset description	These will be produced for each case study summarising the findings for each of the carbon intensive sectors and providing indications of pressing actions and sustainability considerations to support the sustainable transition at the national and EU levels. These will be the main output of T5.3
Creators of Asset	DBFZ, UNIT, WR, BAM, TECNALIA, PC, FVA, KE
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Policy makers: A overview of the current policy instruments impacting the case studies will support to adapt and develop these further + overview of opportunities for policy instruments to integrate and support a sustainable transition to a circular bioeconomy. Industrial players: Overview of prospective policy instruments that could be implemented in the future and have impacts on their business cases Civil society: Overview of policy instruments influencing the sector + what policy instruments could support the development of the sector.
Intended exploitation route	The path towards exploitation will be by way of the IMPLEMENT conference (M28) co-creation workshop and presented to selected regional, national and EU policy makers in six policy roundtable discussions in the partners' respective countries, in the context of the DEPLOY conferences (M30-M34). A copy of the recommendations will also be produced and published on the resources tab on the project website. Let alone being highly disseminated through the project's social media channels.

The actions needed for the exploitation of Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Actions needed for the exploitation of Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results	All SUSTRACK Partners	M36

6.3 Case study analyses

The exploitation plan for Case Study analyses is presented in Table 14.

Table 14. Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses

Asset description	Four (4) sectors were identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system and they include; the construction sector, the textile sector, the (fine) chemical sector, and (d) the plastic sector. The objective for this will be to test whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings will also contribute to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allow for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes will be validated during the IMPLEMENT conference.
Creators of Asset	BAM, CIRCE
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All Stakeholders.
Intended exploitation route	This will be achieved through capacity-building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). These will be held in Italy UNIT/FVA; Spain- TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT. Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the build-up to these capacity-building activities will be made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Case Study analyses are presented in Table 15.

Table 15. Actions needed for Case Study analyses

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results	All SUSTRACK Partners	M36

6.4 WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

The exploitation plan for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities is presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Exploitation plan for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

Asset description	These capacity-building activities will take place to boost the know - how of local stakeholders in each respective partner country and to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural). The results of the policy scenario development and modelling (WP4, T4.3) and the identification of local policy priorities will enable stakeholders to identify actionable steps along the most suitable transition pathway while identifying the pitfalls and opportunities of this pathway in the respective sector (i.e., construction, chemical, textile or plastic sector) and country.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders: Those engaged from each case study, and technical experts for the utilisation of the assessment toolkit prepared in WP2 and capacity-building material from WP4 (Modelling). Multi-actors from case studies: 1. Conclusion and recommendations for each bio-based sector. 2. Guidelines for the identification and review of case study information and results from the environmental, social and economic assessments. Technical experts in each country (participating in the project and/or where a case study has been selected): 1. Dashboard to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition and learn how to apply it. 2. Receiving prepared learning materials (e.g. model tutorials) for the forecast of transition pathways.
Intended exploitation route	This will be achieved through capacity-building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). These will be held in Italy UNIT/FVA; Spain- TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT. Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the build-up to these capacity-building activities will be made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities are presented in Table 17.

Table 17. Actions needed for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Deploy Conferences	Dissemination of results	Partners organising the DEPLOY national conferences as well as owners of the capacity-building materials	During the DEPLOY Conference (M30 - M34) 4 Online seminars (M28 - M32)

6.5 WP6 Co-creation activities

The exploitation plan for WP6 Co-creation activities is presented in Table 18.

Table 18. Exploitation plan for WP6 Co-creation activities

Asset description	3 EU Level conferences will be organized to offer support to partners in specific task-related activities with stakeholders (e.g., co-creation) primarily aimed at sharing both the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK and co-creating stakeholder-oriented content and solutions. 6 national conferences will be organized to fine-tune the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and co-create policy recommendations (both sector- and country-specific). The local DEPLOY conferences will also empower stakeholders through capacity-building activities (T4.3 and T5.2) 2 MML workshops will also be organized. The first MML (M3) workshop will be to engage with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to share methodologies, lessons and findings. And the second MML workshop will be to provide insight to refine the SUSTRACK results and recommendations, thereby facilitating the greatest exploitation of the project outcomes (M30).
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders. Results of co-creation activities.
Intended exploitation route	The major output from these activities will be the creation of actionable knowledge which will then be disseminated through the project's established channels. All these results will be referenced and shared through the resources tab on the project website and will be made available to the wider stakeholder community and the general public during and after the project.

The actions needed for WP6 Co-creation activities are presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Actions needed for WP6 Co-creation activities

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Co-creation activities at INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences	Disseminate the methodology to relevant stakeholders, have it open access	All Partners	During and after the end of the project

6.6 Reports and deliverables

The exploitation plan for reports and deliverables is presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Exploitation plan for reports and deliverables

Asset description	All project activities will be accounted for through the publication of the project results through the project reports and deliverables
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders. Sharing knowledge with all stakeholders regarding project results and activities. Public deliverables will be published on the project website and will be made available to the wider stakeholder community and the general public during and after the project.
Intended exploitation route	This will be achieved through capacity-building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). These will be held in Italy UNIT/FVA; Spain- TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT. Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the build-up to these capacity-building activities will be made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for reports and deliverables are presented in Table 21.

Table 21. Actions needed for reports and deliverables

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Disseminate the overall results to the stakeholders, and have them open access.	All Partners	During and after the end of the project

6.7 Event format package

The exploitation plan for Event format package is presented in Table 22.

Table 22. Exploitation plan for Event format package

Asset description	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced gamified applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MML.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Projects, academia, research, policymakers or other stakeholders organising events such as co-creation workshops, MMLs, and roundtables. Free access to a methodology and guidelines for designing and implementing Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop, co-creation workshops, and roundtables .
Intended exploitation route	The tools and methodologies will be made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for event format package are presented in Table 23.

Table 23. Actions needed for event format package

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Disseminate the methodology to relevant stakeholders, and have it open access.	All Partners	During and after the end of the project

6.8 Scenario simulations generated using the Green Economy Model

The exploitation plan for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model is presented in Table 24.

Table 24. Exploitation plan for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model

Asset description	There will be a baseline and at least one (if not several) policy scenarios available for exploitation and further analysis. The data generated from the scenarios will be shared and made accessible for further processing if required.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Projects, academia, research, policymakers or other stakeholders organising events such as co-creation workshops, MMLs, and roundtables. All stakeholders: Improved insight into the systemic nature of policy action on key socioeconomic and environmental indicators, an estimation of the cost of transition.
Intended exploitation route	The report will describe both the methodological approach as well as an interpretation of results, which increases the understanding of the systemic nature of biobased practices.

The actions needed for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model are presented in Table 25.

Table 25. Actions needed for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Partners organising the DEPLOY national conferences as well as owners of the capacity building materials.	All Partners	After reports were produced; after the end of the project.

7. EXPLOITATION PLANS PER PARTNER

This section summarizes, in tabular format (Table 26.), the assets of the SUSTRACK project that each partner is currently interested in exploiting the most, as well as how they intend to proceed to this end.

Table 26. Individual exploitation plans

UNIT	Results of major interest:
	<p>Along with the project management activities, UNIT will support the development of policy recommendations for the design of sustainable routes towards circular bio-based systems. The identification of policy instruments to support the transition is of major relevance for UNIT. In addition, researchers could use the results of the project to prepare scientific publications but also exploit this acquired knowledge and know-how in new projects with similar objectives. Moreover, regarding stakeholder empowerment activities, UNIT will use its wide network to provide knowledge on the best approaches and methodologies for the sustainable transition.</p>
WR	Results of major interest:
	<p>For WR results of major interest are a further elaboration of approaches (indicators, metrics and models) to monitor circularity at the biobased product level and at the system level. In addition, WR is interested in identifying the best policy instruments to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable bioeconomy. The knowledge generated in the project will be used for scientific publications, acquire new EU projects and provide services to policymakers and companies active in innovations for more circular production systems.</p>
PC	Results of major interest: Reports and deliverables, WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities, WP6 Co-creation activities, Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines
	<p>Our innovation and policy advisors will integrate results/assets in their existing advisory practices to enhance their service portfolio and better support clients in the private and public sectors, while also extending their client base by leveraging the novel collaborations developed during the project.</p>
DBFZ	Results of major interest:
	<p>For DBFZ results of major interest are policy scenarios, policy modelling results and final policy recommendations/action plans. The knowledge created and synthesized here will be used for subsequent publications and policy advice services provided by DBFZ to national and EU policymakers.</p>
FVA	Results of major interest:
	<p>The FVA team will integrate innovative formats (live, online, hybrid)/tools/methodologies of collaboration and stakeholder engagement developed in the context of co-creation and stakeholder empowerment activities (namely INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT, DEPLOY conferences, MML and capacity buildings) in its existing engagement practices, in order to better support future EU funded projects and initiatives and maximize stakeholder engagement, collaboration among projects and, consequently, their impact across Europe.</p> <p>Moreover, FVA, in its role of ecosystem facilitator, will gain substantial knowledge, methodologies and tools for monitoring the transition, which will be exploited in future projects to empower stakeholders at local/regional, national and European levels.</p>

BAM	Results of major interest: Deliverables (reports), papers and internal stakeholder activities at BAM
BAM researchers will be responsible for preparing different reports that will represent the basis for scientific publications. In addition, the results will be disseminated internally at the BAM community in at least three internal dissemination events (including presenting posters at BAM events).	
Unife	Results of major interest:
UNIFE researchers will use the results produced by SUSTRACK for the preparation of several scientific reports and publications. In addition, the results may be taken into consideration for the development of further design activities.	
CIRCE	Results of major interest:
CIRCE will use an analytic hierarchy process methodology to elaborate a list of priorities through pairwise comparisons based on expert judgments. Furthermore, the soil methodology impact will be one of the developments exploited by CIRCE for further activities.	
TECNALIA	Results of major interest:
For TECNALIA, results of major interest will be i) the findings on indicators and monitoring frameworks for assessing benefits and trade-offs resulting from the transition of linear towards circular bio-based value chains and business models and ii) those generated from the assessment of cross-sectoral policy impacts for portfolio scenarios. These key outcomes will help TECNALIA in consolidating its capacities for developing tailored services towards territorial clusters interested in transitioning towards circular systemic solutions at local level.	

8. INNOVATION MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

This section describes briefly how innovation management is articulated in the SUSTRACK project and how the relevant stakeholders interact with the innovation management process.

Innovation is defined as the process, including its outcome, by which new ideas respond to societal or economic needs and demand and generate new or improved products, services or business and organisational models that are successfully introduced into an existing market or that are able to create new markets and that contribute value to society²⁶. Following up on that definition, innovation management is the overall management of all activities related to understanding needs, with the objective of successfully identifying new ideas, and managing them, in order to develop new products and services which satisfy these needs. Although they may be assisted by the innovation and exploitation manager, partners are responsible for managing all innovation-related activities including rights to use background during and after the project; capturing the

²⁶ [Funding & tenders \(europa.eu\)](https://europea.eu)

results; assessing, protecting and managing the IP; dissemination (widely communicating the project outcomes); exploitation (use) of results; and deployment.

Innovation management includes two aspects:

- innovation processes management, and
- change management.

Innovation refers to products and services, business processes, and organizational innovation. Innovation management includes a set of tools that allow project consortium partners to cooperate with a common understanding of processes and goals. Innovation management takes place before the project execution, allowing the project consortium to leverage external or internal opportunities, and use its creativity to introduce new ideas. During the project execution, the innovation management process defines relevant frameworks to ensure that:

- The rights to access and use background and side ground IPs are identified;
- The project results are captured, assessed and protected. Appropriate dissemination, exploitation and communication measures are agreed upon, and final dissemination and exploitation plans are defined.

In SUSTRACK, the main responsible for the innovation management process is PEDAL, which leads Task 6.4.

The key activities of the innovation management process during the project implementation are:

1. Defining (as the first activity in the project) a lightweight innovation management plan to ensure that the related processes are properly organised and managed across project activities. The processes will be designed to ensure that: (i) The rights to access and use background and side ground IPs are identified; (ii) The project results are captured, assessed and protected; (iii) Appropriate dissemination, exploitation and communication measures are agreed, and dissemination and exploitation plans are defined.
2. Liaising and communicating innovation management-related issues within Project Management Committee (PMC) and SUSTRACK Plenary Project Meetings.
3. Maintaining a catalogue of project results and validating the information provided by the partners;
4. Organizing workshops and webinars to (i) Introduce the innovation management activity to the consortium; (ii) Provide guidance on updating the project results and the related dissemination and exploitation plans;
5. Monitoring the exploitation and dissemination plans;
6. Supporting the consortium to select the best protection approaches (IPRs) for the project results;
7. Helping the consortium in defining the most relevant contributions of the project to achieve the expected impacts.

Periodic review meetings will take place to help the consortium in refining the key results and assess the best exploitation and dissemination strategies.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

This initial version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan has presented the main elements of the IPR approach, the methodology employed in this respect as well as provided an overview of the project's assets, background and foreground IP. To facilitate the identification and management of SUSTRACK's assets, a dedicated tool has been elaborated under the supervision of the Exploitation Manager, the IPR Matrix.

The final version of the D6.4 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan report will be submitted in M36 of the project, depicting the latest status in terms of project results' identification, type of protection, ownership and access rights definition, with the support of all partners. The final version of the report will provide more details on the exploitable assets of the project and the framework of their exploitation, to support the sustainability and continuation of SUSTRACK's outcomes.

The Exploitation Manager is responsible for keeping the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan updated. The Exploitation Manager: a) will monitor the project's activities as they evolve; b) will timely capture innovation opportunities that may go unnoticed; c) will identify any potential conflicts of interest and facilitate their resolution before the end of the project. Thus, a proactive smooth post-project exploitation of SUSTRACK results will be fostered.

Project Consortium

